

Substituted-1,8-naphthyridines. Part-V. Synthesis of 2-(1,8-Naphthyridin-2-yl)-4-aryloxy-1-naphthols

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A number of 2-(1,8-naphthyridin-2-yl)-4-aryloxy-1-naphthols (4) have been prepared by coupling 2-(1,8-naphthyridin-2-yl)-1-naphthol (3) with diazotised arylamines. The intermediate compound (3) has been obtained by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1) with 2-acetyl-1-naphthol (2) in the presence of glacial acetic acid containing a catalytic amount of concentrated sulphuric acid. The products have been characterised on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data. The compounds have been screened for antibacterial activity.

1,8-Naphthyridines possess a wide range of biological activities, such as antibacterial¹⁻³, antimalarial^{4,5} and diuretic⁶ activities. Several arylazo compounds are also known to exhibit a wide spectrum of biological activities⁷⁻¹⁰. It was therefore, considered of interest to combine these biologically active units with a view to getting compounds which might possess enhanced biological activities. In continuation of our earlier work on substituted 1,8-naphthyridines¹¹⁻¹⁴, we have now synthesised some 2-(1,8-naphthyridin-2-yl)-4-aryloxy-1-naphthols (4) and evaluated their antibacterial activity. The synthetic approach to the title compounds is outlined in Scheme 1.

The Friedlander condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1) with 2-acetyl-1-naphthol (2) in glacial acetic acid containing a catalytic amount of concentrated sulphuric acid gives 2-(1,8-naphthyridin-2-yl)-1-naphthol (3) in good yield. The structure assignment of 3 was based on its elemental analyses and spectral data. The ir spectrum of 3 exhibited strong broad band at 3 430–3 250 cm^{-1} (phenolic hydroxyl) and an intense band at 1 600 cm^{-1}

(C=N). The spectrum also showed bands at 1 570, 1 510, 1 460, 1 370, 1 230, 1 100, 1 040, 870 and 760 cm^{-1} . In the mass spectrum, the molecular ion peak was observed at m/z 272 which corresponds to the molecular formula $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}$. The spectrum also displayed peaks at m/z 271, 255, 243, 198, 185, 169, 153, 143, 129, 105, 91 and 77. The pmr spectrum also agreed with the proposed structure.

The new 2-(1,8-naphthyridin-2-yl)-4-aryloxy-1-naphthols (4) were obtained by the coupling reaction of 3 with diazotised arylamine at 2–5°. The products are all coloured crystalline solids. The structures of the compounds have been established by elemental analyses and ir spectral analysis. The ir spectra of the compounds manifested characteristic bands in the region 1 620–1 590 cm^{-1} (N=N stretch) and a broad band at 3 420–3 230 cm^{-1} (phenolic hydroxyl).

All the compounds were obtained in excellent yields and physical data of these compounds are recorded in Table 1.

Biological screening: All the compounds synthesised were screened for their antibacterial activity by Vincent and Vincent¹⁵ filter-paper-disc diffusion-plate method. The gram(+) and gram(-) bacteria employed for the tests were *Streptococcus albus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, respectively. Out of the fourteen compounds only five compounds (4; sl. nos. 6, 11, 12, 13 and 14) were found to possess antibacterial activity. The remaining compounds were found inactive towards the bacteria tested. Five compounds were active against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. However, the degree of inhibition varied both with the compound as well as with the bacterium. Compounds of sl. nos. 12 and 13 were more active, while the rest (sl. nos. 6, 11 and 14) were intermediate in their activity. It is also clear

TABLE I—2-(1,8-NAPHTHYRIDIN-2-YL)-4-ARYLAZO-1-NAPHTHOLS (4)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
1.	H	>250	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	76.51 (76.69)	4.21 (4.25)	14.83 (14.89)
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	210	70	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	76.81 (76.92)	4.59 (4.61)	14.31 (14.35)
3.	<i>p</i> -OH ₂	>250	75	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	76.85 (76.92)	4.59 (4.61)	14.30 (14.35)
4.	<i>m</i> -OOH ₂	201	78	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	73.72 (73.89)	4.41 (4.43)	13.70 (13.79)
5.	<i>p</i> -OOH ₂	230	84	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	73.73 (73.89)	4.40 (4.43)	13.69 (13.79)
6.	<i>m</i> -OH	210	67	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	73.38 (73.46)	4.03 (4.08)	14.23 (14.28)
7.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	>250	60	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂	68.34 (68.40)	3.52 (3.56)	16.57 (16.62)
8.	<i>m</i> -Cl	160	75	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₄ OCl	70.08 (70.15)	3.60 (3.65)	13.58 (13.64)
9.	<i>o</i> -COOH	>250	60	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	71.35 (71.42)	3.83 (3.80)	13.31 (13.33)
10.	<i>m</i> -COOH	>250	62	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	71.32 (71.42)	3.82 (3.80)	13.29 (13.33)
11.	<i>p</i> -SO ₂ H	240	68	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	63.08 (63.15)	3.53 (3.50)	12.33 (12.28)
12.	<i>p</i> -SO ₂ NH ₂	265	65	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂ S	63.21 (63.29)	3.69 (3.73)	15.31 (15.38)
13.	<i>p</i> -4,5-Dimethyl-pyrimidin-2-aminosulphonyl	>250	67	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₇ O ₂ S	64.11 (64.17)	4.02 (4.09)	17.39 (17.46)
14.	<i>p</i> -5-Methylisoxazole-2-amino-sulphonyl	>250	69	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂ S	60.61 (60.68)	3.71 (3.73)	15.58 (15.67)

from the present investigations that the hydroxy substituent and compounds containing sulphur atom are responsible for antibacterial activity.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. The purity of all the compounds was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (nujol) were run on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra on a 60 MHz Varian spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a Varian MAT CH-7 instrument.

2-Acetyl-1-naphthol (2) : It was prepared according to the procedure of Joshi and Shah^{1a}.

2-(1,8-Naphthyridin-2-yl)-1-naphthol (3) : A mixture of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1; 0.1 mol) and 2-acetyl-1-naphthol (2; 0.1 mol) was refluxed in acetic acid (25 ml) in the presence of a catalytic amount of concentrated sulphuric acid for 3 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and poured onto crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, (85%), m.p. 257° (Found : C, 79.31 ; H, 4.38 ; N, 10.22, C₁₈H₁₂N₂O requires : C, 79.41 ; H, 4.41 ; N, 10.29%).

2-(1,8-Naphthyridin-2-yl)-4-arylaZO-1-naphthols(4) : Appropriate arylamine (0.1 mol) was dissolved in HCl (1 : 1, 30 ml) and cooled to 0–5°. Cold sodium nitrite solution (20%, 10 ml) was gradually added with stirring, keeping the temperature below 5°. The

resulting diazotised arylamine solution was added with stirring to a cold solution of 3 (0.1 mol) in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 40 ml) below 5°. The resulted reddish orange reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h and the precipitate formed was filtered and washed with water till neutral. Products were air-dried and crystallised from ethanol as reddish orange crystals.

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